

Influence of School Climate on Work Motivation and Efficiency of Basic Education Teachers

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Abstract:- School climate is an integral indicator leading to teachers' effectiveness in school. This study calls to address the relationship of school climate on work motivation and efficiency of basic education teachers. This study used a descriptive – correlational design. There were 70 basic education teachers from the Basic Education Department of Misamis University as my respondents. School Climate Questionnaire, Teachers' Work Motivation Questionnaire and Teachers' Teaching Efficiency Questionnaire were used to determine the level of school climate and teachers' work motivation and teaching efficiency. Result revealed that the school climate is highly favorable and the teachers are highly motivated and efficient. The school environment is conducive and provides opportunities for career development. Thus, having seminars, workshops and great collaboration activities may drive teachers to work efficiently.

Keywords:- Basic Education Teachers, Conducive, Teaching Efficiency, School Climate, Work Motivation.

I. INTRODUCTION

School climate refers to the quality and character of school life. It is based on patterns of students', parents' and school personnel's experience of school life and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning practices and organizational structures (Jayaweera, 2015). It refers to school life's consistency and atmosphere and involves factors such as school traditions, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning, leadership and organizational structures (Cohen 2009, Petrie 2014). School climate refers to the nature and character of school life in relation to expectations and beliefs, interpersonal and social relationships and organizational procedures, systems and culture (Guiney, 2018).

School climate is one of the most significant factors in solidifying an effective learning environment (Lacks, 2016). In the study of an international education studies, the finding proves that work motivation affects positively and significantly teacher job satisfaction. Previously reported that the form of motivation affecting satisfaction is motivation on the admission of achievement, opportunity to reach an achievement, career, responsibility grant, and opportunity to progress more (Arifin, 2015). Motivation and self-esteem of employees in any organization are of great importance. The effect of school climate is closely associated with teachers' work performance and their ability to innovate and to integrate new ideas into their practices (Shah, 2016)

The school climate was important to cause one's job as well as affect the working efficiency. According to the research studies of teachers' job satisfaction, found that the school climate is an integral indicator leading to effectiveness in school. If the teachers were satisfied in work practice in school, that work practice would be easily successful (Wang, 2016).

Positive school climate is central in improving teacher performance and student learning, and to reduce teacher's turnover or intentions to leave the profession (Aldridge, 2016). Teaching and learning situation in schools seems to be a function of the atmosphere of the school and how efficient is the teacher. School climate is a set of unique characteristics of a school. These characteristics distinguish one school from another (Riyadi, 2015). Attitudes, or the way that teachers feel about the teaching profession, may change over time, so it is important to determine if those entering the teaching profession have high levels of efficiency from the onset (Taştan, 2018).

Recent studies on teacher motivation in education have explored different reasons for new teachers to join the profession, factors that motivate and de motivate teachers, the impact of teacher motivation on their teaching, the relationship between teacher motivation and student motivation, and the measures by which teacher motivation can be increased in different working scenarios (Hettiarachchi, (2015). Motivation involves both extrinsic and intrinsic types. One must intrinsically be motivated before accepting new challenges followed by intrinsic motivation for the best achievement. (Nusenu, 2015).

Teacher motivation is a construct that has received significant attention in mainstream education during the last few decades. It is defined as the process that initiates, guides, and maintains goal-oriented behavior. At first, instead of direct measurement, specific conditions must be created and subsequently, the changes in behavior are observed (Stacho, et. Al., 2015). It is generally assumed that motivation influences people's attitude and performance at work. Teacher motivation is directly linked to the instructors' desire to take part in the pedagogical process and interest in sharing their knowledge with the students (Nagrath, 2019)

Teachers' teaching efficiency has been highlighted across numerous research studies as a major variable that affects students' academic. Primary school teachers and teacher applicants at Curuvaca University do not find themselves productive in designing and implementing the teaching process based on various prior knowledge and skills,

learning speed, and level of reasoning, learning styles, and multiple intelligence activities (Gürkana & Doğanay, 2019).

When teaching efficiency is viewed in a wider and holistic sense, incorporating every element of the classroom from lesson delivery to classroom environment becomes important. This includes creating organized and orderly classroom, establishing expectations, inducing students' cooperation in learning tasks, and dealing with the procedural demands of the classroom (Jaffurs, 2017). This view of teaching performance contrasts to a more narrow view of classroom management as it deals with just discipline and control the wider view of teaching performance shows increased engagement, reduction in inappropriate and disruptive behaviors, promotion of student responsibility for academic work, and improved academic performance of students (Ayub, Hussain & Ghulamullah, 2018).

II. METHOD

This study used descriptive-correlation design. Descriptive-comparative research is used to formalize the logic of case-oriented comparative research and elaborates on an analytic approach centered on its principles (Ragin, 2014). The design can help the researcher seek for the significant relationship between school climate to basic education teachers' work motivation and work efficiency.

The respondents of this study were 70 basic education teachers from Misamis University. They were identified through purposive sampling. The respondents were based on voluntary participation. The respondents were made to understand the nature of their participation by reading and explaining to them the terms and conditions specified in the inform consent form to be made.

III. FINDINGS

A. Level of School Climate

The study revealed that the teachers were very favorable with the school climate (M= 3.59; SD 0.53) (Table 1). The school has a very conducive environment for learning. It caters the various needs of diverse learners.

This means that the school provides good sense of values and systematic strategies that are essential to the school's leadership strategy. This result also implies that the institution is providing opportunities for students to create progress and self- direction towards their academic fields. The institution also promotes safe and secure setting not only for the teaching force but as well as for the students. The teachers also exhibit respect and support with each other.

TABLE 1. LEVEL OF SCHOOL CLIMATE

Variable	Mean	SD	Remarks
Leadership	3.73	0.45	Very Favorable
Academic Excellence and Outcomes	3.63	0.49	Very Favorable
Student Behavior and Discipline	3.53	0.60	Very Favorable
Environment	3.51	0.55	Very Favorable
Faculty Relations	3.55	0.55	Very Favorable
Overall	3.59	0.53	Very Favorable

Note: Scale: 3.25-4.00 (Very Favorable); 2.50-3.24 (Favorable); 1.75-2.49(Less Favorable); 1.00-1.74 (Not Favorable)

B. Level of Teachers' Work Motivation

The respondents level of work motivation is highly motivated (M= 3.48; SD = 0.55) (Table 2). This means that the teachers are highly capable of doing their work responsibly because they have high self- motivation. They had high incitement in addressing immediate concerns faced in school.

This finding indicates that teachers felt that they have liberty to use their initiatives in doing their works. Immediate support and assistance from their colleagues also provokes them to do better. Teachers also believe that pedagogy provides them with an opportunity to grow professionally and enhance their various skills. Additionally, proper compensation and recognition encourage them to do their work certainly.

TABLE 2. LEVEL OF TEACHERS' WORK MOTIVATION

Variable	Mean	SD	Remarks
Working Environment	3.27	0.55	Highly Motivated
Collegial Relations	3.55	0.55	Highly Motivated
Work Life	3.68	0.47	Highly Motivated
Reward Evolution System	3.40	0.62	Highly Motivated
Overall	3.48	0.55	Highly Motivated

Note: Scale: 3.25-4.00 (Highly Motivated); 2.50-3.24 (Motivated 1.75-2.49(LessMotivated); 1.00-1.74 (Not Motivated)

C. Level of Teachers' Teaching Efficiency

Teachers level of teaching efficiency is very satisfactory (M = 4.43; SD = 0.13) (Table 3). The respondents are productive in doing their work that made them to attain their respective goals in class. Teachers are efficient in achieving what they intended to accomplish.

This result means that the teachers provide realistic and attainable learning outcomes to students. They furnish various teaching strategies and interesting activities that enrich learning discussion. In addition, the teachers provide clear instructions to students in doing specific tasks. They also demonstrate mastery of the subject matter and good command of the medium of instruction.

TABLE 3. LEVEL OF TEACHERS’ TEACHING EFFICIENCY

Variable	Mean	SD	Remarks
Teaching Efficiency	4.43	0.13	Very Satisfactory

Note: Scale: 4.51-5.00 (Excellent); 4.00-4.50 (Very Satisfactory); 3.00-3.99 (Satisfactory); 2.00-2.99 (Fair); 1.00-1.99 (Poor)

D. Significant Relationship between the Level of School Climate and Teachers’ Work Motivation

The Pearson Product – Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in testing the significant relationship between the level of school climate and teachers’ work motivation (Table 4). All the variables in level of school climate and teachers’ work motivation with $p < 0.05$ are significantly related. However, academic excellence and outcomes and working environment ($r = 0.224$; $p = 0.053$) and collegial relations ($r = 0.216$; $p = 0.062$) are not significant.

The data imply that the level of school climate is significantly related to teachers’ work motivation. This means that the more the school climate becomes better the teachers’ work motivation gets higher. However, there’s no significance between academic excellence and outcomes and working environment and collegial relations. This means that regardless of the academic excellence and outcomes these will not affect their working environment and collegial relations.

TABLE 4. TEST OF SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE LEVEL OF SCHOOL CLIMATE AND TEACHERS’ WORK MOTIVATION

Variable	R value	P value	Remarks
Leadership and:			
Working Environment	**0.347	<0.01	Highly Significant
Collegial Relations	*0.271	0.019	Significant
Work Life	**0.491	<0.01	Highly Significant
Reward Evolution System	**0.296	<0.01	Highly Significant
Academic Excellence and Outcomes and:			
Working Environment	0.224	0.053	Not Significant
Collegial Relations	0.216	0.062	Not Significant
Work Life	**0.357	<0.01	Highly Significant
Reward Evolution System	**0.415	<0.01	Highly Significant
Student Behavior and Discipline and:			
St Working Environment	**0.380	<0.01	Highly Significant
Collegial Relations	**0.494	<0.01	Highly Significant
Work Life	**0.518	<0.01	Highly Significant
Reward Evolution System	**0.586	<0.01	Highly Significant
Environment and:			
Working Environment	**0.390	<0.01	Highly Significant
Collegial Relations	**0.319	<0.01	Highly Significant
Work Life	**0.527	<0.01	Highly Significant
Reward Evolution System	**0.428	<0.01	Highly Significant
Faculty Relations and:			
Working Environment	**0.357	<0.01	Highly Significant
Collegial Relations	**0.469	<0.01	Highly Significant
Work Life	**0.579	<0.01	Highly Significant
Reward Evolution System	**0.501	<0.01	Highly Significant

Note. * $p < 0.05$ (significant); ** $p < 0.01$ (highly significant)

E. Significant Relationship between the Level of School Climate and Teachers’ Teaching Efficiency

The Pearson Product – Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in testing the significant relationship between the level of school climate and teachers’ teaching efficiency (Table 4). Respondents’ academic excellence and outcomes and teaching efficiency ($r = 0.237$; $p = 0.049$) is significantly related. However, leadership and teaching efficiency ($r = 0.068$; $p = 0.576$), student behavior and discipline and teaching efficiency ($r = 0.047$; $p = 0.696$), environment and teaching efficiency ($r = 0.027$; $p = 0.824$) and faculty relations and teaching efficiency ($r = 0.109$; $p = 0.371$) are not significantly related.

The result implies that to what will be the academic excellence and outcomes will influence the teaching efficiency. Inversely, the leadership, students’ behavior and discipline, environment and faculty relations will not influence teaching efficiency.

TABLE 5. TEST OF SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE LEVEL OF SCHOOL CLIMATE AND TEACHERS' TEACHING EFFICIENCY

Variable	R value	P value	Remarks
Leadership and Teaching Efficiency	0.068	0.576	Not Significant
Academic Excellence and Outcomes and Teaching Efficiency	*0.237	0.049	Significant
Student Behavior and Discipline and Teaching Efficiency	0.047	0.696	Not Significant
Environment and Teaching Efficiency	0.027	0.824	Not Significant
Faculty Relations and Teaching Efficiency	0.109	0.371	Not Significant

Note. * $p < 0.05$ (significant); ** $p < 0.01$ (highly significant)

IV. DISCUSSION

School climate is considered as school's heart and soul. It is a social setting or learning environment that offers a variety of activities for students' learning advancement (Lacks, 2016). School climate is an important factor in the success of students and the learning with the high quality teaching practices of teachers. It's also a position promoting common values and beliefs (Vukičević, J. P., Prpić, M., & Mraović, I. C., 2019).

Institutions have to preserve their favorable school environment in order to promote a positive quality of school life for students with a good character. Improving the supportive school environment is also a need to be considered from time to time. It may be beneficial to minimize disruptive behavior, increase performance and academic achievement of the students. In addition, institutions also need to look after its physical set-up and the value of respect of students to teachers that emphasizes the relationship of the students to their teachers.

The motivation of teachers is linked to the attitude of teachers towards teaching, their desire to participate in pedagogical processes within the school, their involvement in student discipline and control of the processes in the classroom (Absar & Jameel, 2017). This study is supported with the study of Sehar & S Khurram (2019) which states that encouragement and motivation of the teachers to take part in decision making inevitably leads to better result for themselves and the institution. Teachers were primarily responsible for ensuring holistic growth of the children. To fulfill this function depended solely on timely promotion and other motivational factors, these include teachers' participation in decision-making, recognition by educational officers and good working conditions (Ndijuye & Pambas, 2019).

Timely promotion of teachers, pay their salary arrears, check upward their compensation benefits and the terms of service is a need to continue and improve of the institution. Teachers have to develop intrinsic motives that will help them to stay with their career and may lead them toward professional improvement and development.

Teaching efficiency means getting the maximum effectiveness for the effort that the teacher puts in. An efficient teacher shows productivity in the way he does things, the way he handles his class and his time to do things (Li-Ying & Cheng, 2015). A teacher is efficient in teaching if he has the ability to develop relationships with other teachers and if he has the dedication and passion towards his work (Geng, 2018).

The teachers help the students' parents mold their lives and their future. They are the one who directs and molds the students' way in life to attain their goals and dreams. Hence, teachers have to love teaching and be more passionate about their work, which involves investing in the learning progress of students. They also need to express enthusiasm and commitment that may help them to be efficient in providing lasting knowledge and skills.

The institutions environment greatly affects its teachers' motivation and productivity to participate. Work motivation of teachers will develop optimally if the school climate is conducive (Ramlani, 2016). The teachers who are working with commitment and passion consider the recognition they receive for their works as important. The lack of recognition and encouragement in the organization is a critical factor that determines the work motivation of teachers (Fidan, 2015).

Schools' needs to create a favorable climate and will try to manage in order to create an atmosphere that fosters the spirit and excitement of the work of the teacher. School environment must satisfy and cater the needs of the teachers in order to keep the teachers motivation at work.

The school environment has a significant impact not only on the achievement of the institution's goals, but also on the performance of teachers. In this sense, the school environment leads a positively to teacher performance development and growth (Ramlani, 2016). School who display a positive environment for teaching influences the performance of the teacher positively, while school who displays negative environment negatively influences the performance of the teacher (Lacks, 2016).

School climate conditions give teachers the opportunity to be more creative in their duties that also provides them to improve the quality of work so as to improve the performance of teachers optimally.

V. CONCLUSION

The school environment is conducive and provides opportunities for career development where teachers are very motivated and highly productive in exploiting their skills and knowledge to do their career. It is also found out that school climate greatly affects teachers work motivation and teaching efficiency. Hence, if the school is unsuccessful in fostering conducive environment teachers will be unmotivated and ineffective in demonstrating learning progress to students and may not promote a successful and healthy co-teacher relationship

Based on the findings and conclusion, it is recommended that the administrators may have professional development opportunities for teachers especially in teaching. Administrators may plan an activity introducing the various teaching styles to teachers through seminars and workshops. This is to help the teachers how to be more productive and responsible in doing their works. In addition, institutions may continue to create favorable school climate that significantly contributes to the improvement of teachers' work performance. To teachers, they may create great collaboration with others not only mentally but as well as emotionally. This may help them to attain intended learning outcomes and employ healthy relationship with one another.

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